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Complexities in Rural Entrepreneurship in India

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Abstract

Majority of population in India lives in villages. The financial growth of our nation fundamentally depends on the progress of rural areas and the standard of living of villagers. Rural entrepreneurship plays a very important role in the economic development of a country as well as of the citizens. The greater parts of rural entrepreneurs are ignorant of technological development, entrepreneurial skills etc and this is due to problems like illiteracy, lack of training and experience, Shortage of finance and agriculture inputs. The purpose of this paper is to recognize the key complexities faced by rural entrepreneurs. The main Objectives of the paper are to examine the problems in rural entrepreneurship in India. The study peeks at the socio-cultural, educational and legal hurdles for rural entrepreneurship in India. A wide-ranging literature review of secondary data sources was assumed as relevant to the stated objectives of the study. The paper generally stands on secondary data and some observations for the recognition of the issues and for this purpose various articles, journals and reports were reviewed. The complexities identified in the research or findings are scarce financial resources, Lack Of Infrastructural Facilities, Marketing Problems, No comprehension towards I.T, Meager understanding of accounting, Difficulty in complying with various legal formalities, Absence Technical Knowledge, Low Class Goods, Human Resources Problems. The research paper opens the scope for other researchers to do the study on therapeutic measures to eliminate the complexities found.

Key words: *Financial growth, entrepreneurial skills, lack of training, rural entrepreneurship, Therapeutic measures.*

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INTRODUCTION

Electronic banking (e-banking), the newest channel for the delivery of banking services, has almost transformed branch banking into a virtual one-stop-shop. The definition of e-banking varies amongst researchers partially because electronic banking refers to several types of services through which bank customers can request information and carry out most retail banking services via computer, television or mobile phone (Daniel, 1999; Mols, 1998; Sathye, 1999). Turban et al.(2004). describes that e-banking offers electronic services that allow customers to check the balances in their accounts, transfer funds among accounts, pay bills electronically as well as apply for loans, download information about accounts into their own computers, trade stocks or mutual funds, look at images of their cheques and deposit slips .

The rural region is habitat to nearly 72 percent of the India's 1.1 billion people, a greater part of which are poor. The majority of the rural people depend on rain-fed agriculture and fragile forests for their livelihoods. Agriculture therefore plays a fundamental function in the existence of a nation. It is the strength of our monetary structure. Agriculture not merely endow with foodstuff and raw material but also service prospects to a very large percentage of inhabitants. It is the agricultural zone that nourishes nation trade. Agricultural goods like tea, sugar, rice, tobacco, spices etc. comprise the core part of India's exports. Thus, it helps to reduce the adverse balance of payments and save our foreign exchange. From the above, explanation it may be concluded that agriculture occupies an important place in the development of an economy. It is in fact, a prerequisite for economic development. Entrepreneurship, in general, and rural entrepreneurship, in particular, has become a dynamic field of research in the last two decades. It seems therefore timely to present a quantitative survey of the literature in this area³.

Undoubtedly Entrepreneurship is capable of bringing in revolution in rural development. Entrepreneurships if instilled effectively in rural area it would definitely, be influential, in resolving the difficulties of unemployment, scarcity, financial discrimination, under exploitation of rural competence, echelon of standard of living and would result in enriching rural areas. A few committed persons or NGOs can become medium for motivating and educating rural people towards the cause of strengthening rural areas, as there are lots of opportunities and strengths, which are needs to be identified and build on them to convert them into entrepreneurial enterprise. It is very important to enable rural population to think positively & creatively and if they will progress with such standpoint and with the help of accurately guided hard work would definitely lead in an age of rural entrepreneurship.

The decisive values for entrepreneur for the rural area intensification are- most advantageous use of neighboring resources in an entrepreneurial endeavor by rural inhabitants - improved distributions of the ranch produce for rural affluence, entrepreneurial employment for rural residents to lessen prejudice and endow with other livelihood to minimize the rural migration .

Growth in rural area is often associated with entrepreneurship. Organizations and persons encouraging rural expansion currently observe entrepreneurship as a tactical advancement interference that might speed up the rural progression. Moreover, organizations and persons appear to have the same opinion on vital requirement to endorse rural entrepreneurship. Rural entrepreneurship have bundle of payback such as - employment opportunities, cutback on

migration of rural inhabitants, unbiased provincial development, Arousing the rural youth, enhanced standard of living, endorsement of artistic society, diminution on social problems, etc.

Literature Review:

1. Alsos, Ljunggren & Pettersen (2003) – Norway, Exploratory study of 16 case studies on triggers for new business activities by existing farmers: with goals – rural sociology perspective: to sustain or expand farm to support more family members e.g. pluriactive farmer , opportunity perspective: to utilize existing resources (human capital, material resources) , resource-based perspective: to exploit new biz ideas.
2. Bertauz & Crable (2007) - India , Case study of how an NGO, whose educational meetings to inform villagers on the use of methane gas for heating, lighting & cooking from its biogas plants, became an opportunity for women to meet collectively to form a co-op for jewelry-making, textile weaving and other handicraft businesses as well as obtained training in other skills e.g. nursing, construction and other trade skills provided by the government.
3. Bhaskaran (2004) - Australia , Case study on stakeholder approach to introduce new crop (wasabi farming): Ant: Jap firm approach its current supplier of green tea on sources of cultivated wasabi. Conversation on farming conditions & market opportunities for the crop led farmer to seize opportunity to prepare a trial crop with Jap firm providing the financial, technical and export support. IV: Farmer investigated potential growing sites with appropriate climate, terrain & geographical conditions for growing wasabi & leased a small plot to grow the crop. Farmer obtained financial support & seed funding to undertake R&D from local government.
4. Chrisman, Gatewood & Donlevy (2002) - US ,Empirical study tested if the economic impact from counseling activities to entrepreneurs in rural & urban areas had different results. No significant differences were found, implies that a high-quality program that is offered by the Small Business Development Center can meet the needs of the majority of entrepreneurs & aspiring entrepreneurs regardless of geographic location.
5. Terjesen (2007)- India, Case study on opportunity identification and new venture creation by director of an NGO: Ant: during a visit to village on the installation of a drinking water pump, the Director noticed at villagers used pot fumigation to catch rats for food Intervention: he developed a better rat trap with the help of a mechanical engineer in the city. In a pilot test with 15 rat catchers, the new trap was found to be more efficient. He obtained funding for its commercialization and a factory was set up. Outcome: 50 young, unemployed women were chosen to work in the factory to produce the traps, who were also given ownership to the factory from the launch of a microcredit revolving fund. 400 traps were produced a month and 1500 villagers were chosen to use new steel traps to start new businesses in catching rats. New factories were established in multiple villages with similar arrangements.

Objectives:

1. To recognize the key complexities faced by rural entrepreneurs.
2. To examine the problems in rural entrepreneurship in India.
3. To peeks at the socio-cultural, educational and legal hurdles for rural entrepreneurship in India.

Research Methodology:

A wide-ranging literature review of secondary data sources was assumed as relevant to the stated objectives of the study. The paper generally stands on secondary data and some observations for the recognition of the issues and for this purpose various articles, journals and reports were reviewed.

Complexities in Rural Entrepreneurship

1. Financial dilemma – scarce resources

One of the biggest evils faced by rural entrepreneurs is deficiency of funds. Key complexities that the rural entrepreneurs have to face are; poor sales due to lack of purchasing power of rural people, short of funding to establish business enterprise, abridged profits owing to competition, pricing issues, rigorous tax regulation, dearth of security for loans, complicatedness in raising money through equity, reliance on users for loans. All these evils generate a complexity in raising funds all the way through loans.

Chief basis of funding in rural areas are loans from regional rural banks or from zamindars, however, the rate of interest charged by them are generally too high to be afforded by rural people and they have inadequate assets for collateral securities. These all problems create a difficulty in raising money through loans. landlords in Punjab proved to be major source of finance for rural entrepreneurs but the rates of land are reduced due to global recession so they also lack hard cash now a days. Some banks have not ventured out to serve rural customers because banks are expensive to be reached by rural customers and, once reached, are often too poor to afford bank products. Poor people often have insufficient established forms of collateral (such as physical assets) to offer, so they are often excluded from traditional financial market. Government is providing subsidies to rural areas but due to high cost of finance, these subsidies are not giving fruitful results¹.

Despite the fact that Government has different organizations for this function, but the outcome is not positive and to the echelon anticipated. To name few Industrial Finance Corporation of India (IFCI), Industrial development bank of India, Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India (ICICI), Small Scale Industry development bank of India (SIDBI) are nationalized institutions that are serving rural entrepreneurs. These institutions are providing aid for establishing of new business along with support for rejuvenation and development of existing ones but their terms and conditions are too austere to be knobbed. Also, Government is offering subsidies to rural region, but owing to high cost of finance, these subsidies are not providing prolific effect. Today microfinance serves as one of the successful programme not only in bringing the poor into the gamut of formal financial system but also in alleviating various problems of rural areas like poverty, unemployment, disempowerment among women, lack of finance facility etc. In India, the Microfinance programme geared up after the intervention of NABARD and several governmental agencies².

2. Lack Of Infrastructural Facilities

Though the Government has made sufficient efforts to encourage rural entrepreneurship, the escalation of rural entrepreneurs is meager and this is due to the fact that there are no suitable and adequate infrastructural facilities available.

Infrastructure facilities comprise transport facilities like bus, train etc, which is helpful for the entrepreneur to transfer goods from one place to another but this amenities are very poor in the rural area. Communication facilities comprise the telephone; fax, internet facilities, entrepreneur

fails to envelop supplementary region to expand company places because of short of these facilities.

3. Marketing Problems

Rural entrepreneurs are dealing with strong competition from the big groups and city entrepreneurs and are unable to contend with them owing to short of standardization, branding and superiority of the products. This is the foremost difficulty the marketers go through in rural areas and this may be because the cost of production is high in rural areas due to high cost of raw material. Ultimately this gives rise to the severe Competition from large scale units and hence generates complexities for the survival of new rural business. The new business enterprise has restricted funds and consequently cannot manage to pay for heavy advertisement and publicity. Also they don't have any accepted brand name beneath which they can trade their products. The agricultural goods are also not standardized and graded.

Rural entrepreneurs are being cheated and exploited by the middleman on whom they are mostly dependent for selling their products. These middleman keep large amount of profit as rural entrepreneurs don't have any knowledge of marketing tactics, as they are less educated and also don't have any means to reach the market directly due to lack of transportation and warehouse facility.

4. No comprehension towards I.T:

The literacy rate among the rural consumer is very low and as a result Information technology is almost absent in rural areas. Entrepreneurs' mostly depend on internal associations that promote the stream of produce, services, information and ideas. The strength of family and personal relationships in rural population can for a moment be supportive but they may also present barrier to successful trade associations. Business transactions may perhaps get less than scrupulous independence and intercommunity enmity might lessen the extent for local support. The manufacturers are not united in their opinion towards marketing their goods since they are extensively scattered and untrained.

5. Meager understanding of accounting:

As discussed above the literacy rate among the rural consumer is very low; they have meager understanding of various business transactions and maintenance of records associated with it.

6. Difficulty in complying with various legal formalities:

Rural entrepreneurs find it extremely difficult in complying with various legal formalities due to illiteracy and unawareness. At the time of inception of the business, entrepreneurs have to comply with government complex bylaws, associated with business license and clearance certificates for pollution, etc, but due to the low instructive echelon of rural entrepreneurs, they come across various difficulties in fulfilling these bylaws.

7. Absence Technical Knowledge:

The expansion of rural entrepreneurship is rigorously hindered due to absence of technical knowledge among rural entrepreneurs. Also training facility is not available in these areas. There is also lack of awareness among rural entrepreneurs, about how to acquire technical knowhow

and in many cases the quality production is hampered if the nature of production needs some specific technical skills to operate, as rural entrepreneur are deprived of these skills

8. Low Class Goods

A vital dilemma in development of rural entrepreneurship is the production of substandard goods due to low quality of raw materials & unavailability of standard paraphernalia.

Nowadays buyers are more aware of the quality of the products and rural entrepreneur are unable to produce quality products as compared to urban entrepreneurs and therefore unable to face competition.

9. Human Resources Problems

Dearth of skilled workers & labor turnover are another major problem in rural areas. This is because either the workers are not trained and experienced & those who are competent migrate to city for better prospects. People will move into an area because they find it attractive, but as more people move in, crime and congestion increase until at some point a balance is reached. In the bloodless world of economics, that can be reduced to a formula. But it doesn't help you find ways to maintain the things you like about a place when other people like it, too⁴.

In this scenario entrepreneurs of rural areas have to make available on job training, as finding skilled workers is too difficult. But providing training is also not a trouble-free job as workers are mostly unqualified and they have to be educated in local language. The businesses in rural region are not only set up just to seize benefit of economical cost of labor but also to carry out an incorporated rural growth. Subsequently rural entrepreneurs must not look at rural area as their marketplace, they ought to see the challenge in urban areas and be geared up for them. Rural entrepreneurs are mostly not that ground-breaking in their beliefs. There is a common belief that young generation in rural areas have modest opportunity, and therefore several of them either work at farm or migrate to urban land.

Another problem is the pessimistic outlook and milieu of the relatives, culture and support organism. It is not at all encouraging as it suppresses the idea of pursuing entrepreneurship as a career among rural people. It possibly would be due to poor understanding of entrepreneurial prospects and awareness about it. Incessant stimulus is required in case of rural workers, which can be sometimes intricate for an entrepreneur to execute. Three possible ways to introduce support and supplement local resources are: to build a technical assistance budget into all grants and designate either a cohort of consultants or lead (existing) agency/institutions for all new projects, to form learning networks comprised of grantees with similar or complementary goals to help share experiences and learn from each other, conduct more staff training for project directors, requiring all its principal investigators to assemble at least annually for budget and management workshops, a project fair, and presentations⁵.

Key findings:

Key complexities that the rural entrepreneurs have to face are;

- Poor sales due to lack of purchasing power of rural people,
- Short of funding to establish business enterprise,
- Abridged profits owing to competition,

- Pricing issues,
- Rigorous tax regulation,
- Dearth of security for loans,
- Complicatedness in raising money through equity,
- Reliance on usurers for loans.

Another problem is the pessimistic outlook and milieu of the relatives, culture and support organism. It is not at all encouraging as it suppresses the idea of pursuing entrepreneurship as a career among rural people.

Dearth of skilled workers & labor turnover are another major problem in rural areas. The literacy rate among the rural consumer is very low and as a result Information technology is almost absent in rural areas.

Infrastructure facilities comprise transport facilities like bus, train etc, which is helpful for the entrepreneur to transfer goods from one place to another but this amenities are very poor in the rural area.

Limitations/ Scope for future work:

The research paper is limited to study of complexities in rural entrepreneurship, but it opens the scope for other researchers to do the study on therapeutic measures to eliminate the complexities found.

Conclusion:

Rural entrepreneurs' role is indispensable to eliminate the poverty in the rural areas. In rural areas greater part of the population is not prepared to invest in the entrepreneurial venture as for them it is unbelievable to accept that entrepreneurship can also become their career. Apart from these other complexities identified in the research are scarce financial resources, Lack Of Infrastructural Facilities, Marketing Problems, No comprehension towards I.T, Meager understanding of accounting, Difficulty in complying with various legal formalities, Absence Technical Knowledge, Low Class Goods, Human Resources Problems.

These circumstances can be changed if the focus of the government is more on rural entrepreneurs for the development of the country. Government should make available separate financial fund for rural entrepreneurs, proper infrastructure amenities should be provided, should organize particular training programmes of rural entrepreneurship, etc.

Rural entrepreneur must be aggressive and competent in the local & international market. Rural entrepreneurs play a very crucial role in economic development of India. Rural entrepreneurship is the means of transforming developing country into developed country. Rural entrepreneurship is the key for elimination of poverty from rural India. For that reason, there should be additional pressure on incorporated rural advancement agenda.

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